

PHOTO ESSAY: TIBETAN WOMEN'S ORNAMENTS IN RGYAB LUNG (JIALONG) VILLAGE,
RTA NAG MA (HEIMAHE) TOWNSHIP, MTSHO SNGON (QINGHAI) PROVINCE, PR CHINA

Sgrol ma yag སྐྱོལ་མ་ཡག་ (Zhuomayou 卓玛优)*

ABSTRACT

I describe the generational uses, attitudes toward, and division of ornaments, particularly coral necklaces, by a Tibetan herding family in Rgyab lung (Jialong) Village, Rta nag ma (Heimahe) Township Town, Gser chen (Gonghe) County, Mtsho lho (Hainan) Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture, Mtsho sngon (Qinghai) Province, China.

KEYWORDS

Tibetan coral necklaces, Tibetan property division, Tibetan herding family, Tibetan ornaments

INTRODUCTION

In 1995, one of my paternal cousins helped Mother give birth to me in our winter pasture adobe house. Mother once said, confusing me, that Gu de skyid was my mother. When I asked for an explanation, Mother said she helped when I was born and added that when I was a very young child, I called Gu de skyid "Mother."¹

In about 2004, my parents paid one of my cousins to take them in his pick-up truck to the county town to purchase candies, beverages, biscuits, and new clothing for the coming Lo sar 'Tibetan New Year'. At dusk, after a long day of herding in the mountains, my brother ('Brug lha rgyal, 1993) and I tied the yaks in the yak enclosure, drove our sheep² back into the sheep enclosure, and then climbed to the top of the yak enclosure to watch for car lights. We were excitedly awaiting the return of our parents. Meanwhile, our sister was cooking. Several cars passed before a car finally turned toward our house. We jumped down from the wall and ran to our house's door and then to the car.

We took the boxes and plastic bags full of what our parents had bought from the car to our house. I took the light ones while my brother, father, and mother carried the heavy ones. After we finished, the cousin said his family members were waiting for him, and he had to leave. My father thanked him and gave him some cash.

My sister poured tea in bowls for my parents first and then us. Next, she put a plate of beef on a table that we sat around. It was near the stove. She handed bowls of noodles to each of us. As we sat around the table, I grew even more eager to see what my parents had bought and had no interest in eating.

Father asked me to open a white plastic bag, so I opened it and discovered a sheepskin robe with an ornamental *me cha* 'lighter' for my brother, a pair of silver earrings and a sheepskin robe for my sister, and a pair of shoes and a plush fabric robe for me.

Father told us to put on our new clothes. My sister and brother were delighted with their new clothes and ornaments. Sister also had coral necklaces and mother's *glo gzar* and *bzho bzung* for the

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¹ Later, Gu de skyid became a nun. In 2020, she lived with her mother (b. 1936).

² My family stopped raising sheep in 2008, because we did not have enough people to herd both sheep and yaks. My oldest sister had married and moved to live with her husband, and my brother and I were in school.

upcoming Lo sar celebrations. I liked my new shoes and robe, but I felt it was unfair that my siblings had ornaments while I did not.

When Lo sar Eve came, Sister and Brother wore their ornaments, which looked nice, so I bravely asked Mother why I had none. Mother replied, "Children should be like children. They don't wear ornaments like adults."

I yearned to grow up more quickly.

In this paper, I focus on a Tibetan herding family's generational division and use of ornaments, particularly coral necklaces, in Rgyab lung (Jialong) Village, Rta nag ma (Heimahe) Township Town, Gser chen (Gonghe) County, Mtsho lho (Hainan) Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture, Mtsho sngon (Qinghai) Province, China. Rta nag ma Township consists of four pastoral communities: Rgyab lung (Jialong), Bum pa (Wenba), Brag mchog (Zhihuqu), and Ra 'khyog (Ranhuqu). I describe personal adornments in my family and the local community (mostly my relatives). I give information about the people mentioned in this text, a glossary of non-English terms relating to adornments, and accounts from my maternal grandmother and mother.

At an average elevation of 3,200 meters above sea level, Rta nag ma Township has a land area of 1,157 square kilometers and a population of 4,860 (2017), of whom ninety percent, according to official statistics, are Tibetan.¹ Agriculture is practiced only in Ra 'khyog, where locals cultivate barley, wheat, beans, and canola. Nearly all township families raise yaks, sheep, horses, a few cows, and a few goats.

Rta nag ma Township offices are located in the township seat of Heimahe, which, in 2020, consisted of two main roads lined with several stores. Most other buildings were tourist hotels, owing to the proximity of Mtsho sngon po (Qinghai Lake). The five-grade Rta nag ma Boarding Primary School with some 400 students from Rgyab lung, Bum pa, and Brag mchog communities is also located here. Rta nag ma Boarding Primary School offers classes taught in the Chinese language and classes in the Tibetan language. Consequently, Han residents of Ra 'khyog Village generally send their children to the County Town for schooling.

I am from Rgyab lung Village that had about 1,197 (335 households) in 2020.²

¹ Data from, <https://bit.ly/3ke8PVb> (accessed 26 July 2020).

² Data obtained from the village leader in 2020.

FIG 1. Location of Rgyab lung Village.¹

FIG 2. People in the text.

Name	Dates	Relationship to Sgrol ma yag
Bo mo thar	?	maternal great-grandfather
'Brug lha rgyal	b. 1993	brother
Bsod nams bde skyid	b. 1997	paternal cousin
Gnam skyid yag	b. 1944	maternal grandmother
Klu mo tshe ring	b. 1988	sister
Mkha' mo yag	b. 1987	maternal aunt
Mtsho mo	b. 1966	maternal aunt
Rdo kho	1941-2008	maternal grandfather
Sgro b+ha		maternal great-grandmother
Sgrol ma mtsho	b. 1968	mother

¹ This map is a compilation of images: <https://bit.ly/3jHC4PVm>; Mtsho sngon Province (Lincun, derived from: File:Map of Province in China 630000 青海省.svg, CC BY-SA 3.0 July 2020), Mtsho lho Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture <https://bit.ly/2Blyd9U>, and Gser chen County <https://bit.ly/39jA4sB> (all accessed 25 July 2020). All but the map of China are edited.

Sgrol ma yag	b. 1995	self
Snying dkar rgyal	?	maternal great-grandfather
Tshe ring lhun 'grub	b. 1981	brother-in-law
Tshe ring rnam lha	b. 1999	paternal cousin

ORNAMENTS

FIG 3 presents images and descriptions of ornaments I refer to in this paper. I include photographs (presented in larger size later) to make it easier to visualize the ornaments, which are challenging to describe in English.

FIG 3. Images and descriptions of ornaments featured in the text.

	The <i>bzho bzung</i> 'milk hook' is made of silver or copper and attached to a robe's front. According to locals, there are two sizes. The larger one is a decoration made of silver, and the smaller one is for holding a milk bucket when milking and is commonly made of copper.
	This <i>dmar gdan</i> has three red and black cloth strips on which twenty or so silver bowls are attached to the bride's back as hair decorations. They may extend from the neck to the feet. Local women wear this during weddings. Women who offer tea to deities before the bride entered the house wear <i>dmar gdan</i> .
	The <i>dngul 'dzab</i> is a silver ring or a cone-shaped silver thimble-shaped decoration placed between coral beads to prevent abrasion and decorate the coral necklaces. Locally, blood-red colored coral is most prized. <i>Byur rmying</i> 'old coral' is considered the best coral and is most expensive, while <i>byu ru so ma</i> 'new coral' is comparatively inexpensive.
	<i>Dung</i> are silver, shell-shaped ornaments attached to a <i>dmar gdan</i> that women wear on the back of their robes.
	My mother wears this <i>shing ma mo'i mig</i> 'eye of the wooden ewe', a yellowish-brown carnelian with coral necklaces and prayer beads as a decoration. She maintains that coral with cracks or an appearance that suggests it was "eaten by insects" are more valuable than other coral because only real coral has cracks.
	Locally, there are two types of <i>glo gzar</i> : (1) The <i>tshes ris jan</i> is a silver, crescent moon above a sun decorated with coral that hangs from the sash at the right or left hip. (2) The <i>char mgo ma</i> is a silver bow above a square decorated with coral and turquoise. Many local women no longer wear the large, heavy <i>glo gzar</i> . Instead, the less intricate, lighter ones are preferred.
	<i>Ja la</i> are red cloth fringe underneath <i>tsheg bstar</i> (FIG 25) and <i>dmar gdan</i> .
	<i>Rna lung</i> 'earrings'. Round flat gold earrings were popular locally for many years, but today, most local women prefer to wear new-style earrings, as shown in this photograph.
	Only a few local women wear coral <i>skag bcings</i> 'belt' made of cloth and leather decorated with silver, coral, and turquoise. Instead, most wear silver <i>skag bcings</i> , as shown in this photograph.

Tsheg bstar are panels a woman wears above her waist on her back. Locals generally think the larger a coral bead, the better. However, for making *tsheg bstar*, small beads are considered best.

Skying khab 'brocade'.

Kha btags are cloth strips representing purity and good fortune given to guests, religious personages, and others to show respect.

Local men and women wear *mchong* 'carnelian' (bottom center) in necklaces.

Decorative *me cha* 'lighters' are adornments worn by local men. Few local women wear *me cha*.

PERSONAL ACCOUNTS

The five accounts below are from my maternal grandmother, who comments on a Muslim who stayed for several days (~1960) in her home, secretly selling otter pelts and coral to locals, and describes ornaments during her daughter's engagement (~1970); my mother, who gives details on her ornaments both before and after her marriage; my sister's experience with ornaments before and after her marriage'; and my own experience with a necklace of coral beads from my mother's and maternal grandmother's necklaces and local coral ownership practices.

ACCOUNT ONE: My maternal grandmother commented on a Muslim merchant who stayed with her family and ornaments she received from her family before her marriage:

When I moved to your grandfather's home, my parents gave me a few small coral necklaces, a sliver *tsheg bstar*, a *dmar gdan*, and several robes. During the engagement, my parents asked my husband's family for three coral necklaces, but they just brought two.

In about 1960, your grandfather and I bought three coral necklaces from a Muslim merchant, who spent several days in our home while secretly selling otter pelts and coral to locals. He gave a lot of fruit to my children, so they liked him. He asked if we would like to exchange one yak for some big coral necklaces before he left. I was excited about this, but my father-in-law disagreed.

ACCOUNT TWO: My maternal grandmother describes ornaments during her daughter's engagement:

In about 1970, my husband and I asked for four big coral necklaces for Sgrol ma mtsho. After one month, the groom's family brought two sheepskin robes, coral necklaces, silver earrings, and so on. Father-in-law asked his elder cousins to come and check if what they had brought was acceptable. I and some of our neighbor women were disappointed with the coral necklaces because we had requested four, but they had brought only three. In the end, the older men ignored our objections and were satisfied with what they had brought for my daughter, and also agreed on an auspicious day for my daughter's wedding.

ACCOUNT THREE: My mother describes her ornaments before and after her marriage:

Before I married, my elder sister (Mtsho mo) and I didn't have our own coral necklaces, so we wore our mother's when necessary. However, we had our own *tsheg bstar*. The coral was mother's, and the silver ornaments were ours. Mother bought the silver from a Muslim merchant during a local festival. We wore *tsheg bstar* and *ja la* that Mother made before Lo sar. I didn't see the coral necklaces, other ornaments, and robes my husband's side brought until my wedding day. I was never asked if I was satisfied. After I married, I had my own coral necklaces, coral *tsheg bstar*, and other ornaments. My mother gave me some of her coral necklaces, a sheepskin robe, and a woolen hat when I moved to my husband's home.

ACCOUNT FOUR: I (Sgrol ma yag) describe my sister's experience with ornaments before and after her marriage.

When my sister, Klu mo tshe ring, was eighteen, she married and moved into her husband's home. On the day of engagement, the groom's side brought four boxes of Huzhu¹ liquor and thirteen large bolts of cloth, each of a different color. Cloth materials included wool, synthetic fabrics, and *skying khab* 'brocade'. Besides, 2,013 RMB was offered as part of the marriage proposal for my sister. My parents, paternal grandfather, and several elder cousins came and asked those who had come to provide three big coral necklaces, other ornaments, and several robes after *skyid sdug bcol ba*.²

A month later, the groom's father communicated that they would bring what had been requested in two days. The groom's father and one of his cousins brought all that was required, except for the coral necklaces. Instead, they brought three old coral necklaces that belonged to the groom's mother.

When our cousins and neighbors came to inspect Sister's new robes and ornaments, the women focused on the coral necklaces, *tsheg bstar*, *skag bcings*, and *glo gzar*. Mother and the other women expressed disapproval. Grandfather sarcastically said it was a shame that the daughter-in-law had taken all the mother-in-law's coral necklaces, which meant they now needed to honor their promise.

The groom's father apologized to my parents, grandfather, and elder cousins and promised to purchase new coral necklaces before the wedding. After several discussions, they agreed upon an auspicious date. However, no new coral necklaces were purchased.

A few days before Sister's departure, Mother gave her one of her coral necklaces, two *dngul 'dzab*, and one of her *shing ma mo'i mig* that had been given to her by her mother. At this time, Klu mo tshe ring had nine coral necklaces that our parents had bought from a Muslim businessman during a local festival in about the year 2000 for 5,000 RMB in total. She thus had ten coral necklaces and two turquoise and carnelian necklaces. After the marriage, the groom's family gave my sister and her husband furniture, tents, and livestock, signifying that they were a new, independent family. This ended the issue of new coral necklaces because it would have been a significant financial burden on the newly married couple to purchase such necklaces.

ACCOUNT FIVE: One night before school, my mother commented on giving me a necklace with coral beads from her and my maternal grandmother's necklaces:

It's good that you have one string of coral, even if you never marry. I'm getting older, so it's okay if I wear fewer coral necklaces. I gave your sister some necklaces when she was married. I don't know if your

¹ Huzhu Tu (Mongghul, Monguor) Autonomous County, located in Haidong City, Mtsho sngon Province, is famous for barley liquor production.

² A time during the engagement process when the bride's family entrusts their daughter to the groom's family. The bride's parents acknowledge their daughter's shortcomings and then ask the groom's side to promise not to physically or emotionally abuse her.

brother's future wife would like to wear coral necklaces. If she doesn't, then the other ornaments like *dmargdan* and *glo gzar* might be yours. Young women look nice when they wear coral necklaces, and coral also has the power to protect you from disease.

Afterward, I wore my necklace as I would an amulet until I went to live in a large city, joined a gym, and participated in group activities such as parties. In the city, people noticed my coral necklace and asked questions, some of which made me uncomfortable, for example, about my ethnicity, birthplace, religious beliefs, political matters, and so on. I stopped wearing it to avoid this, other than when I went to parties and other group activities where I knew there would be no awkward questions.

I never asked my parents, especially my mother, if this coral necklace belonged to our family or me. During the 2019 winter holiday, I forgot to wear my necklace when I went home. Mother noticed and asked what I had done with it. I explained that I had forgotten to wear it but that it was safe in my dormitory.

Mother said, "It's good for your well-being, but it's yours. It's up to you to do whatever you choose with it."

Most local women control the coral necklaces of their families. In my family, my mother makes the decisions about the division of coral necklaces. For example, the night that Mother gave me a coral necklace, she made the decision herself. She did not ask Father. In contrast, Mother often deferred to Father. For example, one of our neighbor's daughters met my sister in the mountains while they were herding and invited her to join them and some other young people at an overnight gathering to be held in her home. She explained that her parents would not be there. Sister asked Mother to talk to Father and request permission for her to attend the gathering. Eventually, permission was granted, and Sister joyfully joined them.

TRANSFER OF ORNAMENTS

There are no fixed rules about giving ornaments to children. This is especially true for mothers. I have two examples of this. First, when children leave their parents to marry, they are no longer part of their parents' family. Parents give livestock, clothes, and ornaments as gifts to the child who is marrying and leaving home. They also ask the groom or bride's family to buy clothing and ornaments for their children, such as sheepskin robes, woolen robes, and coral necklaces. Clothing and ornaments signal a family's social status. If a child's future family is poor, they request less. For instance, when one of my paternal cousins married in 2019, her family requested few clothes and ornaments for her, knowing her husband's family did not have much livestock or other property.

Second, mothers with unmarried daughters are usually older and inclined to wear fewer ornaments themselves. Consequently, they may give some of their ornaments to their daughters. For example, my paternal cousin, Bsod nams bde skyid, who married in 2019, has two siblings who are also married. Their mother has given all her ornaments to the three of them. However, though my mother plans to give her ornaments to my brother and me, she currently remains fond of ornaments and continues to wear them.

CONCLUSION

Grandmother told me that in about 2003 she spent approximately 5,000 RMB on coral necklaces for one of her daughters before she married. In 2019, one of my uncles paid around 12,000 RMB for three coral necklaces for his son's bride. Mother and my family's neighbor women agree that, while genuine

coral is valuable, fashionable, and protects from illness, there are few occasions to wear coral. Locally, both women and men only participate in two big festivals - Lo sar and the fifth lunisolar month's fifteenth day. Women often cannot attend because they are busy or rules limit festival participation, e.g., it is taboo to participate in many social events after a relative's death for specified lengths of time.

Local women think just one or two coral necklaces are fine and that imitation coral necklaces are better because they are stylish, attractive, and cheap. These ongoing changes indicate that social value and practices regarding coral are increasingly fluid, especially with widespread access to social media that impacts what is considered trendy and the availability of low-priced, imitation products that closely resemble authentic coral.

PHOTOGRAPHS

FIGS 4 & 5. (L) *Glo gzar char mgo ma* (2020, Rgyab lung Village, Sgrol ma yag). (R) *Glo gzar tshes ris jan* (2020, Rgyab lung Village, Sgrol ma yag).

FIGS 6 & 7. (L) New style *glo gzar* (2019, Rgyab lung Village, Sgrol ma yag). (R) Bsod nams bde skyid wears a *dmar gdan* on her wedding day (2019, Rgyab lung Village, Sgrol ma yag).

FIGS 8 & 9. (L) A Chinese metalsmith made this *rna lung* before my mother married (2020, Rgyab lung Village, Sgrol ma yag). (R) *Ja la* (2020, Rkang tsha County, Bsod nams bde skyid).

FIGS 10 & 11. (L) I wear my coral necklace (2017, Xi'an City, 'Jams dbyangs skyabs). (R) Mkha' mo yag wears her coral necklaces and gold earrings during Lo sar (2020, at her home in Rgyab lung Village, Mkha' mo yag).

FIG 12. My mother made this coral *skag bcings* for me before Children's Day (1 June), when I was in primary school (2020, Rgyab lung Village, Sgrol ma mtsho).

FIGS 13 & 14. (L) I wear my mother's *dmar gdan*. When my grandmother saw this photograph, she commented, "It isn't very attractive because you have short hair and no braids" (2019, at my home in Rgyab lung Village, Sgrol ma mtsho). (R) When Mother married, my paternal grandmother gave her this *dmar gdan* (made by a Chinese metalsmith) (2019, Sgrol ma yag's home, Rgyab lung Village, Sgrol ma yag). Most local mothers give their *dmar gdan* to a special child, for example, the oldest son's wife, the youngest son's wife, or a daughter who marries and stays at home with her parents. My father's older sister said that her parents gave this *dmar gdan* to my father for my mother, because he is the youngest child, who stayed with my paternal grandparents - his parents.

FIG 15. Klu mo tshe ring wears coral necklaces and her mother's *bzho bzung* and *glo gzar* (~2003, unidentified photo studio in Rta nag ma Township, unknown photographer).

FIG 16. Imitation-coral ornaments for sale before Lo sar (2018, Gser chen County Town, Sgrol ma yag).

FIGS 17 & 18. (L) Klu mo tshe ring during a local festival on the fifteenth day of the fifth month. She *khrid pa* 'eloped'¹ the night of the fourteenth day of the fifth month. Consequently, her braids featured one blue and one white *kha btags*, signifying that she had eloped (~2006, unknown photo studio in Rta nag ma Township Town, unknown photographer). (R) Sgrol ma mstho wears an imitation coral necklace during Lo sar (2020, Rgyab lung Village, Sgrol ma yag).

¹ Locally when a daughter elopes and goes to her groom's home, the groom's family asks three women to make braids for the bride. Elder men representing the groom apologize to the bride's family the next morning when they escort her back to her parents' home.

FIGS 19 & 20. (L) *Dung* (2019, Rgyab lung Village, Sgrol ma yag). (R) Klu mo tshe ring wears a coral *skag bcings* her husband made. The ornaments are hers. She also wears a *dmar gdan* because it is the day of her husband's cousin's wedding. She offered tea to deities¹ that day (2017, at her home in Rgyab lung Village, Tshe ring lhun 'grub).

¹ *Ja mchod* 'tea offered to deities'. Locally, when a new bride moves to home, the family chooses a female cousin or a son's wives to offer tea to deities. The woman should be, in the family's estimation, a "good woman," for example, she respects her parents-in-law and her husband, gets along well with neighbors, and so on. It is hoped the new bride will also be a good woman.

FIGS 21 & 22. (L) Above the turquoise, the yellow bead is the *shing ma mo'i mig* that my mother gave my sister (2020, Rgyab lung Village, Tshe ring lhun 'grub). (R) *Dngul 'dzab* 'thimble-shaped silver ornament' (2020, Rgyab lung Village, Tshe ring lhun 'grub).

FIGS 23 & 24. (L) Coral *rna lung* I bought for 300 RMB from a Tibetan merchant in Gser chen County Town. He told me the coral was from Nepal (2020, Xi'an City, Sgrol ma yag). (R) My coral necklace (2020, Xi'an City, Sgrol ma yag).

FIG 25. *Tsheg bstar* were once worn in my home area. My mother also dressed this way during weddings and festivals. Fashion changes and women (including my mother and sister) no longer wear *tsheg bstar*. Mother said she quit wearing *tsheg bstar* in about 2009, after a horse race festival, because a *bla ma* advised women who wore *tsheg bstar* to stop because it was a bad sign for humans to wear ornaments that resembled a demon's coral wings. Mother then used the coral from the *tsheg bstar* to make coral *skag bcings* (2020, image created by Sgrol ma yag).

FIGS 26 & 27. (R) Tshe ring rnam lha wore his *skying khab* 'brocade' robe during his paternal cousin's (Bsod nams bde skyid) wedding. Bsod nams bde skyid wears her *dmar gdan*, *skag bcings*, *glo gzar*, and coral necklaces. Hanging from her right side is a decorative *rgyab dar* 'different colors of sashes with an Endless Knot decoration in the center and hung from the back' (2019, Bsod nams bde skyid's home in Rgyab lung Village, unknown photographer). (L) Bsod nams bde skyid (left) wears her new *glo gzar* and *skag bcings* as she stands with her husband after moving to his home. Many local women wear new-style *glo gzar* and *skag bcings* (2019, Rkang tsha County, unknown photographer).

FIGS 28 & 29. (L) Mother's imitation coral necklace. Mother and neighbor women comment that many locals no longer wear robes and ornaments as in the past, except during festivals and Lo sar celebrations. They add that excessive amounts of cash were once spent on coral and other ornaments but today, imitation coral necklaces are cheap and beautiful. Consequently, there is no need to worry about losing them or if they are stolen because they are cheap. Most imitation coral beads are spherical (2020, Xi'an City, Sgrol ma yag). (R) Mother's coral *skag bcings*. Many young women - myself included - avoid wearing coral *skag bcings* because it is old-fashioned. However, Mother thinks coral *skag bcings* are beautiful. She has changed the shape of this particular *skag bcings* several times (2020, Rgyab lung Village, Sgrol ma mtsho).

FIGS 30 & 31. (L) Bsod nam's bde skyid wears her mother's coral *skag bcings* during Lo sar (2020, Rkang tsha County Town, unknown photographer). (R) *Me cha*. A few years ago, my parents bought this for my brother for Lo sar, but gave it to me later, because it was too small for a man. My parents bought a bigger one for my brother. I wore it during Lo sar until I decided it was a man's ornament (2020, Rgyab lung Village, Sgrol ma yag).

FIGS 32 & 33. (L) Mother's silver *skag bcings* that she purchased in Gser chen County Town for about 900 RMB in 2018. She wears it during Lo sar and on pilgrimage because it is light and simple (2020, Rgyab lung Village, Sgrol ma yag). (R) Mother's silver ring. My mother said this was from one of her brothers. She took it with clothes and ornaments that her family gave her when she moved to my father's home. A turquoise bead was in the center. After she lost it, she replaced it with a coral bead. She enjoyed wearing it during local horse races and the days of Lo sar (2020, Rgyab lung Village, Sgrol ma yag).

FIG 34. *Skying khab* 'brocade' for sale in the county town (2018, Gser chen County Town, Sgrol ma yag).

FIG 35. One or two *tsheg bstar* may be worn. *Tsheg bstar* often consist of lines of coral and turquoise (not affixed in this photograph) of varying number - framed in cloth. A silver *tsheg bstar* panel consists of small round flat silver discs framed in cloth. Local women wore *tsheg bstar* during Lo sar, at weddings, and on the fifth month's fifteenth day. Bsod nams bde skyid's mother made the *tsheg bstar* in the photograph, which features cloth fringes and small metal bells. It was made when Bsod nams bde skyid was a child and featured *bsgrig gdan* on the edges. A plastic flower is at the bottom center.

TIBETAN TERMS

'brug lha rgyal འབྲུག་ལྷ་རྒྱལ།	me cha མེ་ཅ།
'jams dbyangs skyabs འཇམ་མས་དབྱེངས་སྐྱབས།	mkha' mo yag མཁའ་མོ་ཡག
bo mo thar བོ་མོ་ཐར།	mtsho lho མཚོ་ལྷོ།
brag mchog བྲག་མཚོག	mtsho mo མཚོ་མོ།
bsgrig gdan བསྐྱིག་གདན།	mtsho sngon མཚོ་སྔོན།
bsod nams bde skyid བསོད་ནམས་བདེ་སྦྱིད།	ra 'khyog ར་འཁྱོག
bum pa བུམ་པ།	rdo kho རོ་ཁོ།
bzho bzung བཞོ་བཟུང།	rgyab dar རྒྱལ་དར།
dmar gdan དམར་གདན།	rgyab lung རྒྱལ་ལུང།
dngul 'dzab དངུལ་འཛེབ།	rkang tsha རྟང་ཚ།
dung དུང།	rna lung རྣ་ལུང།
glo گزار གློ་གར།	rta nag རྟ་ནག
gnam skyid yag གནམ་སྦྱིད་ཡག	sgro b+ha གློ་བྲ།
gser chen གསེར་ཚེན།	sgrol ma mtsho གློ་མ་མཚོ།
ja la ཇལ།	sgrol ma yag གློ་མ་ཡག
ja mchod ཇམ་ཚོད།	shing ma mo'i mig ཤིང་མ་མོའི་མིག
kha btags ཁ་བཏགས།	skyid sdug bcol ba སྦྱིད་སྡུག་བཙོལ་བ།
khrid pa ཁྲིད་པ།	skying khab སྦྱིང་ཁབ།
klu mo tshe ring ལྷུ་མོ་ཚེ་རིང།	snying dkar rgyal སྦྱིང་དཀར་རྒྱལ།
lo sar ལོ་སར།	tshe ring lhun 'grub ཚེ་རིང་ལྷུན་འགྲུབ།
char mgo ma ཆར་མགོ་མ།	tshe ring rnam lha ཚེ་རིང་རྣམ་ལྷ།
mchong མཚོང།	tsheg bstar ཚེག་བསྟར།
mchod kha མཚོད་ཁ།	tshes ris jan ཚེས་རིས་ཅན།

CHINESE TERMS

Gangcha 刚察	Jialong 加隆
Gonghe 共和	Qinghai 青海
Haidong 海东	Ranquhu 然去乎
Hainan 海南	Tu 土
Han 汉	Wenba 文巴
Heimahe 黑马河	Xi'an 西安
Huzhu 互助	Zhihuqu 直乎去